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Inheritance of aroma in four rice cultivars (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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We studied aroma inheritance in four rice cultivars—Della (USA), Shiroikichi (Japan), Hokkaido 270 (Japan), and HB1 (China). These were crossed with nonaromatic cultivars (Koshihikari, Nipponbare) and with each other. Four crosses each for aromatic/nonaromatic and aromatic/aromatic were obtained in 1998.

P₁, P₂, and F₁ plants from all crosses were grown in pots in the greenhouse during the 1998-99 winter season; P₁, P₂, and F₂ plants were cultivated in the field in 1999.

Ten leaves were sampled from individual plants at tillering and cut into 5-mm-long pieces, put into a capped glassware, and stored at -20 °C before aroma evaluation. No more than 20 samples were evaluated in a single day. In this process, 1 g

was measured from each frozen leaf sample, put into a capped test tube, and mixed with 5 mL of 1.7% KOH solution for 10 min at 50 °C. Four to five panelists were asked to classify the samples as either aromatic or nonaromatic by their smell.

The F₁ plants from crosses of nonaromatic/aromatic cultivars were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma in the four aromatic cultivars was recessive (see table). Segregating ratios of nonaromatic to aromatic plants in the F₂ populations from the crosses of Della/Nipponbare ($\chi^2 = 0.011, P > 0.90$), Koshihikari/Shiroikichi ($\chi^2 = 0.031, P = 0.75-0.90$), and Hokkaido 270/Koshihikari ($\chi^2 = 0.009, P > 0.90$) were all 3:1, which indicated the inheritance of a single recessive gene for aroma in Della, Shiroikichi, and Hokkaido 270. In the F₂

population from the cross Koshihikari/HB1 ($\chi^2 = 0.079, P = 0.75-0.90$), the segregating ratio was 9:7, indicating that two recessive genes control aroma in HB1.

The F₁ plants from crosses between any two aromatic cultivars (Table 1) were aromatic; the F₂ population did not segregate for aroma, which indicated that the parents contained at least one common aroma gene. The F₂ data show that Della, Shiroikichi, and Hokkaido 270 each contains a single recessive gene and HB1 has two recessive genes for aroma. Accordingly, the aroma genes in Della, Shiroikichi, and Hokkaido 270 were allelic to each other and allelic to one of two aroma genes in HB1.

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Behavior of parent, F₁, and F₂ populations with regard to aroma.

Cross	Parental leaf aroma rating ^a	Aromatic nature of F ₁ plants	Observed F ₂ plants			χ^2	P
			Total	Nonaromatic	Aromatic		
Della/Nipponbare	+/-	-	120	90	30	0.011 (3:1)	>0.90
Koshihikari/Shiroikichi	-/+	-	109	81	28	0.031 (3:1)	0.75-0.90
Hokkaido 270/Koshihikari	+/-	-	144	109	35	0.009 (3:1)	>0.90
Koshihikari/HB1	-/+	-	182	100	82	0.079 (9:7)	0.75-0.90
Della/Shiroikichi	+/+	+	81	0	81	na ^b	na
Della/HB1	+/+	+	90	0	90	na	na
Della/Hokkaido 270	+/+	+	24	0	24	na	na
Shiroikichi/HB1	+/+	+	76	0	76	na	na

^a + = aromatic, - = nonaromatic. ^b na = chi-square test does not apply.

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